

Image: Hippopx

SHORT TERM MISSIONS

Short Term Missions (STMs) are small travel grants with the aim of:

- Sharing scientific expertise, methodologies, equipment and facilities to harmonise the existing approaches and methodologies within the large OHEJP European network
- Driving the research forward in a collaborative and non-duplicative fashion to strengthen both the scientific capacity within the OHEJP
- Contributing to the future prevention, preparedness, detection and response of the EU to foodborne and other emerging threats across human-animal-environmental sectors.

Stable Intra-specific genomic bacterial classification systems

Theme:
Home Institute:
Mission Hosting Institute:
Duration of Mission:

One Health
[Norwegian Veterinary Institute](#) (NVI), Norway
[Institut Pasteur](#), France
5 days

The aim of this mission was for the researcher to gain knowledge on the usage and design of a stable classification system and nomenclature approach for bacterial strains and to understand advantages and limitations of its use in genomic epidemiology.

Previous isolate nomenclature/classification systems including serotyping and MLST typing do not always satisfy two major criteria: long-term stability and congruence with phylogenetic relationships, which are essential for routine epidemiological surveillance. During this mission, theoretical training was provided by the host institute, to gain deep understanding and practical experience of a novel classification system and nomenclature approach for bacterial strains (cgLIN codes). Training also allowed further understanding of the advantages and limitations of its use in genomic epidemiology.

The STM provided valuable training, allowed knowledge transfer and strengthened the collaboration between One Health partners. Further funding will be sought to continue this valuable collaboration, in order to further develop and expand the nomenclature system for additional bacterial pathogens.

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The STM allowed me to understand and practice applying the newly developed cgLIN bacterial nomenclature system. I now have a better understanding on how the classification system can be used for genomic epidemiology of zoonotic and infectious diseases and able to disseminate this knowledge to other scientists. This will strengthen the activities in One Health to address existing and emerging threats of foodborne and zoonotic agents as well as animal pathogens”

Eve Zeyl Fiskebeck
NVI, Norway

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